

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETING AND WORKING MEMORY

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Abstract. Simultaneous interpreting is a complicated process of translation which happens in the mode of real-time. It not only encompasses online processing of information in working memory, but also the allocation of that information to concurrent tasks. The aim of the research is to identify the difference in performance of interpreters with similar cognitive abilities who have different level of working memory expertise.

Key words: working memory, expertise, simultaneous interpreting, cognitive abilities.

Introduction. Simultaneous interpreting is one of the demanding jobs around the world, it allows people at international conferences or meetings to connect and understand the processing in their own language. This form of interpreting requires comprehending, translating, processing, producing and monitoring of the information. Interpreters are expected to do several cognitive tasks at the same time which also includes reasoning and controlled attention.

The role of working memory in cognitive activities is very crucial. The WM is a fundamental cognitive process and enables people to process and store information temporarily. However, its capacity is limited.

Method. In this study, descriptive research methodology is used to identify whether professional interpreters or tranee students have better working memory. There were 2 groups and one group consisted of professional interpreters while the other consisted tranee students who had less experience in intepreting. All interpreters translated from Uzbek into English.

Selection of the task. Three types of tasks were adminstered. The first one was selected texts based on their level of difficulty. Those texts were recorded and interpreters were to interpret them.

The second task was backward digit span. Participants were expected to listen the backward numbers and write down the numbers in order.

The last task was listening span test. In this one interpeters, first, listened to the sentence and had to determine whether those sencences were logically correct and at the same time remember the last word of the sentence.

These tasks were used to determine working memory capacity in the participants of two groups.

Results. All the data collected from the experiment showed that working memory capacity was the same in all participants regardless of their level of professionalism. However, better performance of interpreting was seen in professional interpreters who had more years of experience in simultaneous interpreting.

The study suggests that better performance cannot be explained by merely the intellectual ability and working memory capacity, but it can be achieved through several strategies and knowledge that interpreters use in the process of interpreting.

Conclusion. From the study it can be concluded that expertise in simultaneous interpreting relies on the acquisition of domain specific skills, but with larger working memory capacity.

Interpreters are highly selective at what they interpret and do not interpret. Based on this they convey a rather detailed information to the audience.

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